

MULTICULTURALISM IN THE INTERPRETATION OF PEARL BAK

Tukhtayeva Farida Ismatullayevna

A senior teacher of the Department

Of English Literature and

Translation studies

Bukhara State University

f.i.tuxtayeva@buxdu.uz

tel: 995550524

Abstract: Introduction: Pearl S. Buck, the renowned American author and advocate for social justice, had a profound understanding of the significance of multiculturalism in society. Through her works, she explored the complexities of different cultures, bridging the gap between East and West, and challenging prevailing stereotypes. This article delves into the theme of multiculturalism as interpreted by Pearl Buck, highlighting her deep appreciation for diversity, her ability to foster cross-cultural understanding, and her impact on the global literary landscape.

Key words: Multiculturalism, stereotypes, cross-cultural, character, individual, intervening, authentic

INTRODUCTION

Cultural Appreciation and Understanding: Pearl Buck's upbringing in China as the daughter of missionaries exposed her to the richness and diversity of Chinese culture. This early exposure led her to develop a deep sense of appreciation for all cultures, breaking down barriers and promoting cultural understanding. Buck's Pulitzer Prize-winning novel, "The Good Earth," is a prime example of her literary exploration of multiculturalism. The novel portrays the life of Chinese peasants, shedding light on their struggles, family dynamics, and cultural traditions. Buck's accurate representation of Chinese customs and traditions not only educated Western readers but also fostered empathy and understanding towards Chinese culture.

METHODS

Shattering Stereotypes: One of the remarkable qualities of Buck's portrayal of multiculturalism is her ability to challenge stereotypes. She confronted prevailing stereotypes about China and its people, offering a more nuanced and authentic perspective. Buck's works presented Chinese characters as fully realized individuals with their own hopes, dreams, and complexities, rather than conforming to Western ideals or exaggerated caricatures. This approach shattered stereotypes and contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of Chinese culture, paving the way for a more inclusive society. One of Buck's most famous works is "The Good Earth," a novel set in rural China. The story follows the struggles and triumphs of a poor, hardworking farmer named Wang Lung. Through Wang Lung's experiences, Buck exposes readers to the social, economic, and cultural aspects of Chinese society in the early 20th century. By providing readers with an authentic portrayal of Chinese life, Buck challenges societal biases and promotes multicultural understanding.

RESULTS

Promoting Cross-Cultural Relationships: Through her writings, Pearl Buck recognized the importance of cross-cultural relationships and encouraged dialogue and mutual respect. Her novel "Dragon Seed" focuses on the intertwining lives of Chinese villagers and American missionaries during the Second Sino-Japanese War. Buck emphasizes the universal values that connect people across cultures, highlighting the shared human experiences of love, loss, and resilience. By depicting the bonds that can form between individuals from different cultural backgrounds, Buck emphasized the potential for cross-cultural understanding and unity.

Buck's emphasis on multiculturalism goes beyond her portrayal of Chinese culture. In her novel "Imperial Woman," she explores the life of Empress Dowager Cixi, one of the most influential figures in Chinese history. Buck's meticulous research and attention to detail allow readers to step into the shoes of Cixi and gain insight into the complexities of imperial life in China. By presenting Cixi as a multifaceted

character, Buck strives to challenge stereotypes and remind readers of the importance of understanding different cultures on a deeper level.

DISCUSSION

Legacy and Impact: Pearl Buck's contribution to multiculturalism in literature extends beyond her portrayal of Chinese culture. Her fiction expanded to include diverse cultures such as India ("Sons," "The Mother," and "A House Divided") and Korea ("Pavilion of Women"). Buck's exploration of these cultures shed light on their unique complexities, challenging readers to question preconceived notions and stereotypes. Her work helped foster a more inclusive world where cultural diversity is celebrated rather than feared or misunderstood.

Throughout her works, Buck's portrayal of multiculturalism is not confined to Chinese culture alone. In her novel "The Hidden Flower," she tells the story of Kweilan, a woman who marries a Chinese merchant and moves to America. Buck explores the challenges faced by individuals attempting to navigate between different cultures, highlighting the difficulties of assimilation and the longing for acceptance.

By weaving multicultural themes into her narratives, Buck champions the idea that embracing diversity is essential for a harmonious and just society. Her characters represent the struggles and triumphs of individuals from various backgrounds, reminding readers of the richness that comes from cultural exchange and understanding.

Pearl Buck's commitment to multiculturalism was not limited to her works of fiction. As an advocate for human rights, she dedicated her life to fostering cultural exchange and promoting understanding between different nations. In 1964, she established the Pearl S. Buck Foundation, which aimed to improve the lives of children in need through international adoption and educational programs.

Buck's legacy as a writer and humanitarian exemplifies the importance of multiculturalism in promoting empathy, acceptance, and understanding. Her ability to transport readers into different cultures allows them to experience, firsthand, the beauty and challenges of diverse societies.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion: Pearl Buck stood as an influential advocate for multiculturalism, using her storytelling prowess to promote cross-cultural understanding and challenge stereotypes. Her diverse body of work not only shed light on different cultures but also served as a bridge connecting East and West. Buck's representation of multiculturalism has left a lasting impact on literature and society, urging us to appreciate the beauty of diversity and embrace the richness of different cultures. Through her work, she continues to inspire readers to embrace multiculturalism, fostering empathy, understanding, and unity in an increasingly globalized world.

Pearl Buck's works serve as a testament to the power of multiculturalism in literature. Through her stories, readers are exposed to a multitude of cultural perspectives, challenging societal biases and promoting a deeper understanding of different cultures. Buck's dedication to multiculturalism extends beyond her fictional narratives and into her philanthropic efforts, making her an inspiring figure and an advocate for a more inclusive world

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